

Welcome to the PALOMERA Survey on Open Access Book Policies!

(Open for participation until 8 October 2023)

INFORMATION FOR PARTICIPANTS

Thank you for your interest in our PALOMERA survey on open access book policies. Please read the following information carefully.

Purpose of study

Academic books continue to play an important role in scholarly production, particularly in the social sciences and humanities. Nevertheless, academic books have not been a focal point for open access policy-makers so far. PALOMERA is an EU-funded project that addresses this challenge.

More information: <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/>

This survey is a contribution to an extensive collection of data on the needs, obstacles and challenges of policy-making for open access books. Based on the evidence given by the survey results, PALOMERA will provide actionable recommendations for the development of open access book policies on the European, national and institutional level. By taking part in this survey, you are making a contribution to the research needed to speed up the transformation of the book market to open access.

Research team

This survey on open access book policies is carried out by Bielefeld University Library, Germany (Project manager: Jan-Philip Tummes). Cooperation partner for this survey is Göttingen University Library, Germany (Project managers: Hanna Varachkina and Malte Dreyer). The project is funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement number 101094270: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094270>).

Study procedure – What exactly awaits you in this study?

Section A: GENERAL QUESTIONS

A1. What type(s) of institution(s) do you work for?

National or regional policy maker

Research funding organisation (RFO)

University or other research performing organisation (RPO)

Publisher

Library

Infrastructure provider

Scholarly society/academic association

I do not work for any organisation

Other

Other

A2. In which country are you located? (If you live in a different country than the location of your primary institution, please use the institution's country here and throughout the survey.)

- Afghanistan
- Åland Islands
- Albania
- Algeria
- American Samoa
- Andorra
- Angola
- Anguilla
- Antarctica
- Antigua and Barbuda
- Argentina
- Armenia
- Aruba
- Australia
- Austria
- Azerbaijan
- Bahamas
- Bahrain
- Bangladesh
- Barbados
- Belarus
- Belgium
- Belize
- Benin
- Bermuda
- Bhutan
- Bolivia, Plurinational State of
- Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Botswana
- Bouvet Island
- Brazil
- British Indian Ocean Territory
- Brunei Darussalam

A3. Are you professionally involved in open access (for example, supporting open access publishing as a publisher or librarian)?

Yes

No

I don't know

A4. How would you rate your expertise in the field of open access? (1 = Novice, 5 = Expert)

1 2 3 4 5

Section B: OPEN ACCESS POLICY

B1. Does your country have a national open access policy?

Yes

No

I don't know

B2. Are open access books included in this national open access policy?

Yes

No

I don't know

B3. Does your country have a policy exclusively dedicated to open access books?

Yes

No

I don't know

B4. Does your institution have an open access policy?

Yes

No

I don't know

B5. Are open access books included in this institutional open access policy?

Yes

No

I don't know

	Not Important	Slightly Important	Moderately Important	Important	Very Important	I don't know
Research assessment and evaluation bodies	<input type="checkbox"/>					

C2. How important *should* the following stakeholders be for the implementation of open access book policies in your country?

	Not Important	Slightly Important	Moderately Important	Important	Very Important	I don't know
University libraries	<input type="checkbox"/>					
University presses	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Scholar-led publishing initiatives	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Commercial publishers (national)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Commercial publishers (international)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Individual researchers	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Scholarly societies/ academic associations	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Research performing organisations	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Research funding organisations	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Research assessment and evaluation bodies	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Section D: ATTITUDES TOWARDS POLICY-DESIGN

D1. An open access policy for books on the national level changes academic publishing for the better.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="checkbox"/>				

D2. An open access policy for books on the institutional level changes academic publishing for the better.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="checkbox"/>				

D3. I am interested in participating in the design of an open access policy for books on a national level.

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>
I don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

D4. I am interested in participating in the design of an open access policy for books on an institutional level.

Yes

No

I don't know

D5. I am aware of opportunities to participate in the processes of shaping a policy for open access books.

Yes

No

D6. I know which stakeholders are involved in designing a national open access policy for books.

Yes

No

D7. I know which stakeholders are involved in designing an institutional open access policy for books.

Yes

No

Section E: ATTITUDES TOWARDS MEASURES TO PROMOTE OPEN ACCESS BOOKS

E1. Publishing an open access book (digital or print) and publishing a closed access book is equally prestigious.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided Agree Strongly Agree

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E2. Authors willing to publish an open access book in my country have sufficient information to do so.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided Agree Strongly Agree

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E3. Authors willing to publish an open access book in my institution have sufficient information to do so.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided Agree Strongly Agree

.....

E4. There are sufficient funding opportunities to publish an open access book in my country.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided Agree Strongly Agree

.....

Separate budget lines for open access and non-open access books

Not Important	Slightly Important	Moderately Important	Important	Very Important	I don't know
<input type="checkbox"/>					

Offers from different publishers can be compared with one another (for example because partial services are shown in price)

<input type="checkbox"/>					
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F7. How important are the following measures for open access books?

Not-for-profit open access scholarly publishing models

Not Important	Slightly Important	Moderately Important	Important	Very Important	I don't know
<input type="checkbox"/>					

Financial support through open access funds

<input type="checkbox"/>					
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Availability of publicly funded technical infrastructures, such as public repositories

<input type="checkbox"/>					
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Availability of commercial technical infrastructures, such as commercial repositories

<input type="checkbox"/>					
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Advice on open access publishing, such as information services or helpdesks

<input type="checkbox"/>					
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Measures to change the reputation-system around open access publications

<input type="checkbox"/>					
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Appropriate programmes for open access books in publishing houses

<input type="checkbox"/>					
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Promoting alternative publication formats and forms such as blogs or living books (bibliodiversity)

<input type="checkbox"/>					
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Section G: FEEDBACK

G1. Thank you for your participation in the survey. Is there anything else you would like to share with us?

Thank you for your participation in this survey!

If you would like to stay in touch with the PALOMERA project and learn about the results of this survey, you can click the following link to be able to sign up for PALOMERA news and invitations to activities: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeqiJMYpCgZmWfaTnN6E8nVWIKKWg_mt9KFJIPXab1Rqqkvw/viewform (external link)

If you have further questions or comments, do not hesitate to contact us: Jan-Philip Tummes, jan-philip.tummes@uni-bielefeld.de, +49 521 106 3798 Hanna Varachkina, varachkina@sub.uni-goettingen.de, +49 551 39 26897 Malte Dreyer, malte.dreyer@sub.uni-goettingen.de, +49 551 39 26897

Grant Agreement number: 101094270 This survey is run by LimeSurvey. Used Resources: Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Universitätsverlage. (2022). Qualitätsstandards für Open-Access-Bücher (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7075761>